

A study on the adsorptive catalytic voltammetry of titanium with salicylfluorone

Xiaoli Zhang, Lizeng Wang* and Dazhong Shen

Department of Chemistry, Shandong University, Jinan, Shandong, People's Republic of China

Manuscript received 4 November 1999, revised 23 March 2000, accepted 8 May 2000

The complexation of titanium-salicylfluorone (SAF) has enabled its trace determination in HCOOH/HCOONa buffer solution containing 1.6% NaClO₃ by linear sweep voltammetry. Catalytic effects of chlorate on the adsorption current of the titanium complex with SAF are determined. The electrode reaction of Ti^{IV}-SAF adsorbed on the surface of the electrode is found to be irreversible. The detection limit and linear relationship are 6.0×10^{-10} mol dm⁻³ and $1.2 \times 10^{-9} \sim 1.6 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm⁻³, respectively. The method has been applied to sample of human hair.

Because of the importance of titanium, a simple and highly sensitive method is required for its determination at low concentration. Cathodic stripping voltammetry (CSV) preceded by adsorptive collection of complex on a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) has been used to determine a number of trace metals. Complexes of Ti with cupferron¹ and with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol² have been reported in Ti analysis of natural waters and biological samples, respectively. In addition, the trace Ti analysis of environmental samples has been achieved using mandelic acid³, solochrome violet RS (SVSR)⁴ and various heterocyclic azo-compounds⁵. Catalytic effects have been usefully combined with CSV to improve the sensitivity, giving limits of detection typically in the picomolar region for platinum⁶ and titanium⁷.

We have already reported the adsorption voltammetry of zirconium⁸ and antimony⁹ using salicylfluorone (SAF) as a complexing agent. In this study we have developed a new method which has advantages over CSV procedures in terms of sensitivity and selectivity. A modification of the method for Ti analysis is possible by utilizing the catalytic effect of chlorate on the reduction of Ti-SAF. The proposed catalytic method enhances the sensitivity of CSV for Ti enabling analysis at the 10^{-10} mol dm⁻³ level.

Results and Discussion

Ti-SAF binary system :

Adsorptive and voltammetric characteristics : Salicylfluorone (SAF) gave a sensitive reduction peak (*p*₁) in HCOOH/HCOONa solution (pH = 3.5), $E_{p1} = -0.82$ V (Fig. 1 curve 2). When Ti^{IV} was added to this solution, a new peak (*p*₂) appeared at a position more negative than that of SAF, $E_{p2} = -0.97$ V (Fig. 1 curve 3). Hence, it is proposed that the new peak resulted from the Ti^{IV} complex with SAF. Addition of Ti^{IV} to the above-mentioned solu-

tion results in an immediate decrease in the adsorptive reduction peak for SAF and an increase in the Ti-SAF complex peak. Under these conditions, a linear relationship was observed between Ti^{IV} concentration and the peak current of *p*₂ in the range 3.6×10^{-8} to 7.2×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ Ti^{IV} for the preconcentration time of 60 s.

Fig. 1. Typical adsorption reduction voltammograms of SAF and Ti^{IV} complex with SAF (1) 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCOOH/HCOONa (pH = 3.5), (2) (1) + $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ SAF, (3) (2) + $3.6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ Ti^{IV} $E_a = -0.30$ V, $t_a = 60$ s, $v = 100$ mV/s

It was found experimentally that the optimum supporting electrolyte was 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCOOH/HCOONa and the optimum concentration of SAF $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for the reduction of the Ti^{IV} complex. In this solution, the peak

current, ip_2 increases upon extending t_a , over a relatively long t_a , adsorption equilibrium was established. ip_2 varied linearly with the potential scan rate, ν , which is a characteristic of the reaction of the adsorbed reactants on the electrode^{10 11}.

The cyclic adsorptive voltammogram of Ti-SAF is shown in Fig. 2. Two cathodic waves appeared at -0.82 and -0.97 V, respectively, and no corresponding anodic wave appeared in the potential range -0.40 to -1.1 V. This implies that the electrode process is totally irreversible.

Fig. 2 Cyclic adsorptive voltammogram of Ti-SAF system. Experimental conditions as in Fig 1 except $E_a = -0.40$ V and $C_{SAF} = 8.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm^{-3}

Influence of foreign ions : Electrochemical inactive ions such as K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} as well as most commonly occurring anions such as Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Al^{III} , Fe^{III} did not react with SAF, so, no new peak appeared. SAF complexes of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Sn^{IV} , Sb^{III} , Ga^{III} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^V were reduced at HMDE and new peaks appeared, whose potentials were as follows : Cu^{II} , -0.20 ; Pb^{II} , -0.58 ; Sn^{IV} , -0.53 ; Sb^{III} , -0.46 ; Ga^{III} , -0.93 ; Zr^{IV} , -0.87 ; Nb^V , -1.04 V. However, the sensitivities of the reductions of these complexes were found to be 30 to 200 times lower than that of the Ti-SAF complex in determination of Ti, so, they did not interfere in the determination of titanium.

Ti-SAF- $NaClO_3$ ternary system :

Effect of chlorate on the reduction of Ti-SAF complex : It is well known that, in some cases, catalysis enhances the current in voltammetry. In the present study, it has been possible to catalytically enhance the sensitivity of determination by adding chlorate to the analytical solution.

From the voltammogram of Ti-SAF system, without and with chlorate, an obvious enhancement of the reduction peak current of Ti-SAF complex in the catalytic method could be observed. The peak current of the Ti complex can be further doubled by increasing the concentration of chlorate as shown in Fig. 3 (curve 1). In fact, the

Fig. 3. Effect of the concentration of $NaClO_3$ on the peak current (1) relationship between ip and C , (2) relationship between ip and $C^{1/2}$; $C_{SAF} = 9.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm^{-3} and $C_{Ti} = 4.4 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm^{-3}

catalytic peak current of Ti complex was found proportional to the square-root of concentration of catalyst, chlorate (Fig. 3 curve 2).

Adsorptive and voltammetric characteristics of Ti complex : By examining the effect of variation of the preconcentration potential, it is found that the reduction peak current was greatest at 0.0 V and it decreased at more negative potentials. The effect of the potential scan rate on the peak current and peak potential was also evaluated. The Ti complex peak current was found to be proportional to the scan rate. The Ti complex peak current increased upon extending the preconcentration time. The shape of the peak was symmetrical with respect to the ordinate axis and the peak half-width was wide.

Electrode process : The symmetry factor (α) and the number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step (n_α) in a totally irreversible interfacial reaction can be taken from peak half-width ($W_{1/2}$) by the equation¹⁰,

$$\alpha n_\alpha = 62.5/W_{1/2}$$

The average peak half-width is 118 mV at different potential scan rates and different concentrations of Ti. From this value, the α value of 0.53 and the n_α value of 1 can be calculated. According to above studies, the processes may be represented by the equations,

Interference : High selectivity is one character of the adsorptive catalytic voltammetry; the catalytic method response to cationic interference is very similar to the non-catalytic one. Table 1 shows the results of several ions and their maximum amount allowed with the measurement of 7.28×10^{-8} mol dm^{-3} Ti^{IV} ; below these ratios, the peak cur-

rents did not change by more than 10%. Many other metal ions, such as Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Al^{III}, Fe^{III} did not interfere with the measurement.

Table 1 Interference of ions and their maximum amount allowed in Ti determination*

	Cu ^{II}	Bi ^{III}	Sb ^{III}	Pb ^{II}	Mo ^{VI}	Zr ^{IV}	Ga ^{III}	Nb ^V
Max amount (μmol dm ⁻³)	1.45	1.74	4.0	14.5	0.4	2.0	1.3	23.2
Times ion/√Ti ^{IV}	20	24	54	200	5	27	18	320

*Error ≤ 10%

Analytical application

The sample of human hair was mixed with mixed acid (HNO₃, HCl, H₂O = 1, 3, 3, 15 ml) and heated on a hotplate at 80° for ~5 h. Then HClO₄ (1 ml) was added to it and heated until the evolution of white smoke. After cooling, the resulting white deposit was dissolved in water and diluted to 50 ml with water. Typical results determined by linear sweep adsorption voltammetry with two successive standard additions for treated samples, and the analysis of samples spiked with known quantities of Ti^{IV} are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of determination of Ti in the samples of human hair

Sample no	Content determined* ppm	Added ppm	Found* ppm	Recovery %
1	0.27	0.30	0.56	96.7
2	0.16	0.20	0.34	90.0
3	0.38	0.40	0.79	102
4	0.21	0.20	0.40	95.0

* Mean of five determinations

Experimental

A voltammetric analyzer (model 79-1, Jinan Fourth Electronic Factory, China) was used. The three-electrode system consisting of a HMDE as the working electrode, a Pt plate as the counter electrode and a SCE as the reference electrode was used. pH was measured with a pH meter (model pHs-2).

A stock solution of titanium (1000 mg cm⁻³) was prepared by dissolving titanium powder (purity 99.9%, 0.5000 g) in H₂SO₄ (5 ml) and HNO₃ (0.5 ml) heated to boiling and diluted to 500 ml with 5% H₂SO₄. Standard solutions were obtained by diluting the stock solution with water. A 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ stock solution of SAF was prepared by dissolving the SAF in ethanol (G.R. 250 ml) containing 6 mol dm⁻³ HCl (10 ml). A 2.0 mol dm⁻³ HCOOH/HCOONa solution was prepared. All the solutions were prepared from triple-distilled water.

Procedure Appropriate Ti^{IV} standard solution was transferred into the cell, then 2.0 mol dm⁻³ HCOOH, HCOONa (2 ml), 40% NaClO₃ (1.6 ml), 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ SAF (40 ml) were added and diluted with triple distilled water (40 ml) and deaerated by N₂ for 10 min. The preconcentration potential, -0.3 V (vs SCE) was applied to a fresh mercury drop. After a preconcentration time of 60 s (stirring), the stirring was stopped, set aside for 30 s and the voltammetric curve was recorded by scanning the potential in the negative direction with a scan rate of 100 mV/s.

References

- 1 V. Gümmei Colos and R. Neeb *Naturwissenschaften* 1986 **73** 198
- 2 J. Zhou and R. Neeb *Fresenius Z Anal Chem* 1990 **338** 34
- 3 H. Li and C. M. G. Van Den Berg *Anal Chim Acta* 1989 **221** 269
- 4 J. Wang and J. S. Mahmoud *J Electroanal Chem* 1986 **208** 383
- 5 J. Zhou and R. Neeb *Fresenius Z Anal Chem* 1994 **348** 724
- 6 C. M. G. Van Den Berg and G. S. Jacinto *Anal Chim Acta* 1988 **211** 129
- 7 K. Yokoi and C. M. G. Van Den Berg *Anal Chim Acta* 1991 **245** 167
- 8 X. Zhang, C. Ma and L. Wang *Fresenius Z Anal Chem* 1995 **351** 618
- 9 X. Zhang, C. Ma, L. Wang and J. Zhang, *Talanta* 1995 **42** 897
- 10 E. Laviron, *J Electroanal Chem*, 1974 **52** 355
- 11 A. P. Brown and F. C. Anson *Anal Chem* 1977 **49** 1589